

Supporting information

Suppressing charge recombination by engineering homojunctions in brookite TiO₂ nanorods for enhanced photocatalytic hydrogen evolution

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Table S1. Power of the light source used for measuring AQY.

Wavelength (nm)	Power (mW cm ⁻²)
316	1.6
334	1.2
360	2.8
369	8.7
386	5.0
402	17.7

Figure S1. N₂ adsorption/desorption type IV isotherms (mesoporous solids) at 77 K for B-US0 (bottom), B-US4 (middle) and B-CU2-US4-HNO3 (top) sample.

Figure S2. (A) Ultraviolet-visible diffuse reflectance spectra (UV-Vis DRS) of B-US2, B-US4 and B-US8 sonoreduced brookite. (B) Corresponding Tauc plots for calculation of band gap according to the base-line method.

Figure S3. HR-XPS spectra of Ti 2p region for (A) B-US0, (B) B-US1 and (C) B-US4, and (D) B-US8. (E) The atomic percentage of Ti^{3+} at the surface of the samples treated with different time of sonication.

Figure S4. HRTEM image of brookite nanorods after copper particle photodeposition and 4 h sonication (B-CU2-US4) in low (A) and high (B) magnification, and after acid treatment (B-CU2-US4-HNO3) in low (C) and high (D) magnification.

Figure S5. Effect of the amount of Cu ions employed in the masking process on the photocatalytic H₂ evolution rate from methanol photoreforming (the number before CU is the amount of copper in wt. % of TiO₂ present in the solution employed for photodeposition). All of the samples are treated with HNO₃ to remove the Cu particles and for simplicity, the prefix "HNO₃" in the sample name has been omitted.

Figure S6. HR-XPS spectra of Ti 2p region for (A) B-0.1CU1-US4-HNO₃, (B) B-0.1CU2-US4-HNO₃ and (C) B-0.1CU3-US4-HNO₃ samples. (D) The atomic percentage of Ti³⁺ at the surface of the samples with different duration of photoreduction reaction.

Figure S7. TEM images of TiO₂ brookite nanorods loaded with Cu photodeposited particles from a solution containing 0.1 wt. % of copper precursor illuminated for (A) 1h, (B) 2h and (C) 3h, and 1 wt. % of copper precursor illuminated for (D) 1h, (E) 2h and (F) 3h.

Figure S8. The size distribution of copper particle based on different loading time and copper salt concentration for photodecomposition. The size distribution of copper nanoparticles is based on TEM image measurements for 100 particles.

Figure S9. The photocatalytic activity of the most active sample (B-CU2-US4-HNO₃) functionalized with 1wt. % Pt in (A) seawater and (B) pure water.

Figure S10. The photocatalytic activity for methanol photoreforming of B-CU2-US4-HNO₃ loaded with 1 and 3 wt. % of Pt.

Figure S11. (A) EDS spectrum of a copper photo-deposited brookite sample after HNO₃ treatment. (B) XPS survey of pristine and the most photoactive brookite after HNO₃ treatment. The detected Si in EDS analysis is impurity from the glass reactor.

Figure S12. CW-EPR spectra of the samples B-US0 (curve a) and B-CU2-US4-HNO3 (curve b) recorded at 77 K and 1 mW of incident microwave power. Sample B-US0 is basically diamagnetic except for a superoxide signal whose magnification is reported in the inset.

Table S2. Spin concentration related to Cu^{2+} species retrieved from EPR spectroscopy measurements for representative brookite samples.

Sample	Cu^{2+} [spin g^{-1}]
B-CU1-US4-HNO3	$1.00 \cdot 10^{-18}$
B-CU2-US4-HNO3	$1.20 \cdot 10^{-18}$
B-CU3-US4-HNO3	$0.65 \cdot 10^{-18}$
B-US4-CU2-HNO3	$2.20 \cdot 10^{-18}$
B-US0-CU2-HNO3	$0.20 \cdot 10^{-18}$

Figure S13. (A) Deconvoluted PL spectra obtained using 3.65 eV excitation energy, and (B) integral of PL peak area of components at 2.58 eV, 2.31 eV and 1.95 eV extracted from PL deconvolution of B-US0, B-US4, and B-CU2-US4-HNO3.